

Patient Experience Management as a Strategic Enabler Improving Patient Satisfaction in Healthcare Services: A Conceptual Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This conceptual analysis synthesizes existing literature to explore patient experience management (PEM) as a strategic tool and valuable indicator for enhancing patient satisfaction in healthcare services. While numerous studies have explored patient satisfaction and experience, there remains a need to integrate these concepts within a unified framework. **Aim:** This Literature review critically examines how these two areas have been extensively studied and proposes a more integrated agenda. Various studies have been written to measure the satisfaction level of patients; however, research rarely explores the relationship with patient experience. **Outcome measures:** This research is grounded in an extensive literature review, identifying key variables of patient experience and patient satisfaction. **Results:** Effective patient experience management implementation leads to improved satisfaction, loyalty, and healthcare outcomes. **Conclusion:** Additionally, this study contributes theoretically by integrating multidisciplinary perspectives and practically by offering strategic insights for healthcare administrators. Future research directions and implications for policy and practice are also discussed...

Keywords: Patient Experience Management, Patient Satisfaction, Healthcare Sector, Conceptual Framework, Healthcare Quality.

INTRODUCTION:

“Health is Wealth”

A decade ago, predictions indicated that India's healthcare sector could become highly valuable, with growth potential similar to other booming sectors, driven by rising health issues. The WHO Constitution states, "Health is considered a state of complete mental, physical, social, and psychological well-being and not purely the absence of disease or illness". Health is the most valuable and intangible asset of mankind. Health is a fundamental right of every human being and is considered a value (Cosma et al., 2020).

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) is the central ministry of the Government of India responsible for formulating, implementing, and monitoring policies related to healthcare facilities and services, public health, and family welfare in the country.

A positive patient experience is paramount when delivering patient-centered care (Sagi et al., 2016). With the rapid growth in research, a diverse and expanding global community, and a shared commitment to outcomes, patient experience has now claimed its place at the heart of healthcare (Wolf, 2016).

Patient satisfaction, the second most frequently mentioned variable, is a measure of contentment based on the perceived quality of healthcare received by a patient (Jha et al., 2017).

Statement of Problem

What are the various patient experience dimensions that influence patient satisfaction in hospitals?

Is there a significant relationship between patient experience management and patient satisfaction?

Research Framework

3.1 Aim:

The aim of this study is,

To examine the wider concept of Patient Experience Management

To analyze various variables influencing patient satisfaction

Develop a comprehensive conceptual framework based on the literature review for linking Patient Experience Management and patient satisfaction

Identify research gaps from existing literature review and future directions

3.2 Research Gap

Patient satisfaction is the gap between patient expectations and experience (Beattie et al., 2015). Despite its importance, the relationship between PEM and patient satisfaction remains fragmented in existing literature. This study aims to bridge this gap by developing a comprehensive conceptual framework.

3.3 Research Objectives

The present study aims to achieve the following objectives:

To critically examine the concept of Patient Experience Management (PEM) and its evolving role in modern healthcare service delivery to measure patient satisfaction.

To analyze the various variables of patient experience based on the available existing literature.

To explore the relationship between Patient Experience Management and patient satisfaction in healthcare services.

To develop an integrated conceptual framework linking Patient Experience Management dimensions with patient satisfaction outcomes.

To identify key research gaps in the existing literature and suggest directions for future empirical research, particularly in developing healthcare contexts.

3.4 Research Design

This study adopts a conceptual/literature review-based research design to analyze existing studies on patient experience management and patient satisfaction.

3.5 Data Collection

Secondary data were collected from different sources, as listed below:

Research papers

Reports

Textbooks

Published materials

Magazines and newspapers

Literature Review

4.1 Patient

Lee (2019) suggested that patients, just like any individual customer, are unique because of their differing diseases and treatments. Patient comes from the Latin phrase “patiens,” from “patior,” which means to suffer or bear.

4.2 Concept of “patient experience management”

Over time, the definition and understanding of patient experience have evolved significantly thanks to the contributions of many academics and organizations.

There is no longer a question that patient experience matters in healthcare today (Wolf, 2016). In the healthcare service design process, consideration of patients’

experience is a priority since the enhancement of care quality can be achieved only through an understanding of patients’ requirements (Lee, 2019). Technological developments also encourage innovative and efficient approaches to measuring patient experience (Sediawan et al., 2023). The patient experience is a multidimensional, multifaceted, and intimately connected concept with several subsections (Oben, 2020).

As a patient’s experience can only be fully understood by each patient with a set of unique feelings, hospitals must engage and interact with patients in order to improve care quality (Lee, 2019).

4.3 Concept of “patient satisfaction”

The field of patient satisfaction has been extensively studied, with various authors contributing to its understanding and development.

In recent years, the focus on measuring patient satisfaction has increased (Cosma et al., 2020).

Patient satisfaction, along with safety, quality, and clinical effectiveness, contributes to the overall patient experience (Jha et al., 2017). Therefore, measuring patient satisfaction with healthcare service quality represents a significant element of a healthcare system’s (HS) overall evaluation, and it is the starting point for creating policies in national healthcare (Cosma et al., 2020). Satisfaction can be defined as a feeling of pleasure that serves as a meeting point between expectations for service and service performance perceived by consumers (Sediawan et al., 2023).

4.4 Relationship Between Patient's Experience and Patient's Satisfaction

In the healthcare service design process, consideration of patients’ experience is a priority since the improvement of care quality can be achieved only through an understanding of patients’ requirements (Lee, 2019). Thus, patients' experiences represent a rich source of invaluable information for designing effective healthcare services (Lee, 2019). Despite its importance, the patient experience lacks a standardized definition, suggesting a need for consensus in future research (Wolf, 2014).

Research Insights

The following table presents a synthesis of key studies on patient experience and patient satisfaction.

Author(s) & Year	Theme	Key Insight
Lee (2019)	Service Design	Patient experience is central to healthcare service design

Jenkinson et al. (2002)	Measurement	Emphasized detailed experience-based questions for monitoring healthcare
Browne et al. (2010)	Measurement Tools	CAHPS enables systematic collection of patient experience data
Gleeson et al. (2016)	Quality Improvement	Highlighted attention required the use of experience data for improving healthcare practices
Jha et al. (2017)	Care Process	Examined patient experience across pre, during, and post-care stages
Doyle et al. (2013)	Outcomes	Linked patient experience with safety and clinical effectiveness
(Sagi et al., 2016)	Outcomes	Pivot survey on patient feedback on their experiences during their hospital stays, showing relationships between different variables
Beattie et al. (2015)	Measurement Tools	Stressed the importance of selecting appropriate measurement instruments
Oben (2020)	Conceptual Understanding	Highlighted the need for a clear understanding of patient experience
Kumah (2017)	Conceptual Distinction	Differentiated patient experience and patient satisfaction
Ross & Venkatesh (2016)	Patient Loyalty	Positive experience enhances patient loyalty
Ahmed et al. (2014)	Healthcare Quality	Established importance of patient experience in quality assessment
Sediawan et al. (2023)	Service Quality	Identified dimensions reflecting patient experience in healthcare
(Wolf, 2014)	Importance of PEM	Patient experience remains a viable, respected and highly embraced part of the healthcare conversation
Sodani et al (2010)	Study on Variable	variables of Healthcare and their positive and negative impact on PS
Bull (2021)	Concept of PEM and PS	‘patient satisfaction’ and ‘patient experience’ are not interchangeable concepts

Variables of Patient Experience and Patient Satisfaction

The variables influencing these choices, selection of Patient Experience and Patient satisfaction have been extensively studied by various authors, each highlighting different aspects of Patient Care.

The findings confirm that Patient Experience Management is a strategic capability that enhances patient satisfaction. Trust and perceived value play critical roles in translating experience into satisfaction. Additionally, digital transformation is reshaping patient experience management. Internationally, most of the studies commenced in the context of Hospitals and the healthcare sector. Developing countries have recently started focusing on measuring various aspects of the healthcare

List of Constructs of Variables					
Socio-Demographic Profile	Hospital Environment & Facilitation	Quality of Relationship	Patients Safety	Patients Personalization (Engagement & Experience of Treatment)	Quality of Health care services (QoS)
Hospital Type	Distance of Hospital	Communication with Doctor	Hygiene Standards	Communication & Language	Waiting Time Management
Length of Stay	Appointment Schedule	Communication with Nurses	Food Services offered	Health Literacy	Regulatory Health Standards
Insurance	Infrastructural Facilities	Hospital Staff Communication and Response	Safety Standards	Patients Centered Care Services	Confidence and Trust
Age	Clinical Guidelines Health Information Systems	Timeliness of Care (TOC)	Cleanliness of the hospital	Effect of Treatment & Care Transition	Treatment Planning and Co-ordination
Gender	Payment Charges	Clarity of Information provided	Medical Equipment	Previous Hospital Experience	Pain Management
Education	Response to Request	Interaction with the physician	Public Health Services	Patient Involvement in Decision-Making (PIDM)	After Treatment Facilities
Marital Status	Pharmacy or Medication Services	Discharge Information	Feedback Facility	Willingness to Recommend	Overall Hospital Ratings
Occupation		Physical comfort	Complaint and their Re-Solution	Support from Family & Friends	
Monthly Income		Emotional Support		Self-reported health status	
Ethnicity		Level of Comfort and Privacy			

Discussion

Statement of Principal Findings

sector, such as patients' experience, patient satisfaction, patient trust, service quality, etc. Despite considerable work undertaken, no comprehensive methodology could be derived for measuring and comparing Patient satisfaction in healthcare and the development of a

structural model is needed that may cover multiple dimensions for the evaluation of patient experience.

Strengths and weaknesses of the study in relation to other studies

Strengths of the study:

Nowadays, increased population growth has resulted in increased continuous patient inflow, rising demand for quality healthcare services. In the Indian context, the increase in the healthcare sector in the private sector demands more focus to measure the effectiveness of healthcare service by measuring different variables of patients' perspectives and patients' experiences. Not enough studies are undertaken to compare the patients' satisfaction in the private sector.

Limitations of the study:

This study is conceptual in nature and is based on an extensive review of existing literature; therefore, it has certain inherent limitations:

Secondary Data: The findings are derived from secondary sources and do not involve primary empirical data, which may limit the ability to validate the proposed relationships in real-world healthcare settings.

Publication Bias: The study relies on previously published research, which may be subject to publication bias and variations in research design, context, and methodology across studies.

Meaning of the study:

There are huge studies regarding patient satisfaction and patients' experiences abroad. But this major issue is not yet effectively addressed in our country. In the Indian context, very few empirical studies are undertaken to study the service quality and patient satisfaction. The previous studies on both global and domestic levels do not have many references to studies on patients' experiences.

There are many factors and dimensions affecting patients' decision to choose a sector for healthcare, but the cost of Healthcare is the main concern for patients receiving the services. In the private hospital sector, almost all facilities are provided, but the cost is too high to be afforded by many of its clients.

This study, therefore, focuses on different variables of patients' experience in private hospitals and aims to identify the factors associated with patient satisfaction. Identified variables were documented and categorized into a design, organizational and outcome variable matrix.

Unanswered questions

Our healthcare systems are always delivering services but rarely bother about the attitudes, needs and opinions of patients. The private hospitals are in such a competitive environment and technological advancement that in order to sustain this edge they are required to provide good quality health and superior services to the patients. Based on earlier studies and an extant literature review, it is evident that a larger number of research studies are undertaken to measure service quality and the measurement of patient satisfaction in a hospital using the

SERVQUAL model, SERVPREF model, both internationally and in the context of Indian Hospitals. However, there are *contextual gaps* in this field of study, which focuses on measuring patient satisfaction based on different variables of patients' experience in private hospitals. The study will contribute to the existing stock of knowledge and to the improvement of the satisfaction level of the patients in private hospitals. Moreover, this study is unique in the sense that it evaluates patients' satisfaction with evaluating various dimensions of patient experience from patient perspectives, considering the unique demographic, cultural, and healthcare service characteristics of the region. This study is therefore undertaken to bridge this research gap by comprehensively examining the dimensions of patient experience management and analyzing their impact on patient satisfaction in the hospital.

Future research (broader aspects)

This section describes the potential of further research in various papers. Every research has its own limitations, owing to different constraints. Each research article includes a note about these limitations.

Author(s) & Year	Focus Area	Future Research Direction
Lee (2019)	Service Design	Further scope to explore relationships among care quality, satisfaction, and value co-creation
Gleeson et al. (2016)	Quality Improvement	Limited studies; need more research on use of experience data in practice
Wolf (2016)	Healthcare Variables	Need to explore diverse variables and healthcare settings
Jenkinson et al. (2002)	Measurement	Need detailed experience-based questions for healthcare monitoring
Ramez (2012)	Measurement Tools	Need development of tools to measure experience and satisfaction
Coulter et al. (2009)	Measurement Methods	Increasing need to study and refine measurement techniques
Kingsley & Patel (2017)	Measurement Tools	Need validated tools for experience measurement
Jha et al. (2017)	Care Process	Scope to study variables like wait-time,

		consultation, and outpatient processes
Guler (2017)	Critical Care	Limited to ICU; scope for broader healthcare settings
Grondahl et al. (2013)	Patient Care Scope	Limited care aspects; need broader evaluation
Wolf & Jason (2014)	Conceptual Clarity	Need for clear definition of patient experience and satisfaction
Oben (2020)	Conceptual Framework	Need standardized approach to measure patient experience
Bull (2021)	Conceptual Distinction	Shift needed from satisfaction to experience-based measures
Ross & Venkatesh (2016)	Contextual Scope	Scope for studies in private hospitals
Cosma et al. (2020)	Patient Satisfaction	Requires more in-depth and context-specific studies
Sediawan et al. (2023)	Population Coverage	Limited sample (maternity/pediatric); scope for broader healthcare segments
Beattie et al. (2015)	Instrument Development	Need for new and improved measurement instruments
Kumah (2017)	Framework Development	Scope to refine models distinguishing experience and satisfaction
Klaus (2018)	Emerging Concepts	Scope for research in luxury/wealth care experience
Birkelien (2017)	Expectation Gap	Need to bridge gap between experience and expectations
Kash et al. (2018)	Strategy Framework	Scope to develop actionable strategies for healthcare managers
Doyle et al. (2013)	Literature Scope	Limited review; scope to expand evidence base
Sagi et al. (2016)	Sample Size	Small sample; need larger and controlled studies

Alasad et al. (2015)	ICU Study	Limited variables; scope for multi-variable studies
Tubić et al. (2023)	Qualitative Scope	Limited constructs; need comprehensive frameworks
Sodani et al. (2010)	Sector Coverage	Limited to public hospitals; need private sector studies
Ahmed et al. (2014)	Data Utilization	Limited insight into use of experience data for improvement
Kash & McKahan (2017)	Comparative Analysis	Scope for comparative studies on experience vs satisfaction

Managerial Implications

The planners and policy-makers for making appropriate policies to improve the situation prevailing in private hospitals

Hospital Administration and Ethical Committee of the hospitals are to implement those policies in the most efficient way possible.

The practitioners in designing effective patient-centric care aspects and the framework of strategies

The researchers in this field and related fields should undertake further study to fill in the gaps in information in the concerned discipline

The Healthcare Quality and Accreditation Bodies to review the existing policy and framework for fresh amendments to the existing policy

The academicians will get an insight into the realities of the problem of the poor satisfaction level of the patients

Government Hospitals or Public Hospitals to frame a healthcare policy to attract people to use public hospitals

Conclusion

Patient Experience Management is a strategic approach that significantly enhances patient satisfaction. This study provides a comprehensive framework for future empirical research and practical implementation.

Patient Experience Management is a vital area to measure patient satisfaction levels, and it is a measurable area of focus. However, not all the dimensions of patient experience influence and measure patient satisfaction. There are various studies made to measure patient satisfaction by using different models of patient service quality. Patient Experience Management (PEM) encompasses multiple dimensions, including Effective communication with healthcare professionals, responsiveness of staff, Education and Experience of Nursing staff, physical environment, administrative processes, Administrative services, emotional support,

Physical comfort and privacy factor and continuity of care. These experiential factors collectively shape patients' perceptions and influence their level of satisfaction, trust, and loyalty toward healthcare institutions.

Furthermore, there are empirical studies on models to measure patients' satisfaction level routed through service delivery and patients' preferences. There is a noticeable lack of context-specific research that systematically examines how different components of patient experience are managed within hospitals and how these components influence patients' overall satisfaction. It will be helpful for policymakers and the administration of hospitals to provide effective patient-centered care services. Prior research largely examines individual determinants of patient satisfaction, but fails to capture the holistic and multidimensional nature of patient experience.

Ethics Approval

This study is based entirely on a conceptual analysis and review of existing literature. It does not involve any primary data collection from human participants, patients, or animals. Therefore, ethical approval from an institutional review board or ethics committee was not required. All sources of information used in this study have been appropriately cited and referenced to ensure academic integrity and avoid plagiarism.

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Author Contributions

Mr Jignesh H. Rana and Dr Belur O. Baxi contributed to the conceptualization, supervision, and critical revision of the manuscript and solely responsible for the conceptualisation, literature review, analysis, and writing of the manuscript and approved the final version. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this study.

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Originality/value

The insights into various aspects of patients' experiences and patient satisfaction were explored in general to achieve a better, deeper understanding. The outcomes of the study may form a basis for deciding the direction of future research...

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